

(2) $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O} \dots 2.8$ gm/lit containing small quantity of HNO_3 soln., found to contain 1.001 mg Cd^{2+} ions/ml.

Determination of Cadmium : A known volume of 1 to 50 ml of soln. No. 2 was taken and diluted (the amount of cadmium was not too much). A freshly filtered soln. No. 1 was added in excess. An orange red or brown red precipitate of cadmium complex was digested on a water bath for 20 min and filtered through a medium porosity sintered glass crucible. It was washed with water several times and then with ethanol, dried at 90° to 105° or in a vacuum dessicator and weighed as $\text{Cd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{S})_2$. The gravimetric factor for cadmium is 0.2585.

Element Analysis—Cd(Complex)	%C	%H	%N
Found	48.8	2.5	12.4
Required	48.4	2.3	12.8

TABLE 1

Determination of cadmium with the ligand

Sl.No.	mg. metal taken	mg. metal recovered	% Error
1	5	4.95	1.0
2	5	4.96	0.8
3	5	5.05	1.0
4	5	5.04	0.8
5	10	10.06	0.6
6	10	10.04	0.4
7	10	9.90	1.0
8	10	10.12	1.2
9	25	25.20	0.8
10	25	25.00	—
11	25	25.40	1.6
12	25	25.20	0.8

Interferences : There is generally no interference by the most common anions such as SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} , CO_3^{2-} , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- and CN^- . Only few cations interfere. These are $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$, $\text{Au}(\text{III})$, Pb , Ag , $\text{Hg}(\text{I})$, $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$, Bi , $\text{Pd}(\text{II})$, $\text{Pt}(\text{IV})$, Ni , Co , $\text{Rh}(\text{III})$, Tl , Ru .

Results and Discussion

The analytical data in table 1 indicate that the ligand can be effectively used as a promising gravimetric reagent for Cd in micro and semi-macro quantities. It is easy to bring the precipitate to a constant weight within 1 hr. The precision was fair and the accuracy was generally within the permissible limits.

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Studies in the Formation of Heterocyclic Rings containing Nitrogen : Part XVII Condensation of 4-Substitutedphenylenediamines with Acetylacetone

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IN our earlier communication¹, we reported the formation of N-(*o*-aminophenyl)2,5-dimethylpyrrole from *o*-phenylenediamine and acetylacetone.

In the present investigation the reaction between 4-substituted-*o*-phenylenediamines and acetylacetone was studied in detail to understand the effect of the substituent on the formation of the pyrrole derivatives (I or II) or a mixture of both. 4-chloro, 4-methyl and 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamines have been chosen for this study.

Equimolecular proportion of 4-chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine and acetylacetone were allowed to react in acetic acid at room temperature. The pure compound isolated from this reaction was found to have N-(*o*-aminoaryl)2,5-dimethyl-pyrrole structure based on its IR and NMR data (see Experimental). This product was identified as N-(2-amino-4-chlorophenyl)-2,5-dimethyl pyrrole (I = R = Cl)².

In a similar manner, 4-methyl-*o*-phenylenediamine with acetylacetone yields a compound having N-(*o*-aminoaryl)2,5-dimethyl pyrrole structure. By comparison with N-(2-amino-4-methylphenyl) and N-(2-amino-5-methyl phenyl)-2,5-dimethyl pyrroles² the above product was found to be a mixture of both isomers (I & II, R = Me). GLC analysis using an authentic sample of I (R = CH_3) as reference compound showed that the present mixture consists of I and II (R = CH_3) in 3 : 2 proportion.

4-Nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine did not react with acetylacetone under similar conditions.

The formation of N-phenyl-2,5-dimethyl pyrrole in excellent yields from aniline and acetylacetone under identical conditions offers a palusible explanation to the present results. Compared to aniline

($K_b = 4.2 \times 10^{-10}$) both *m*-chloro ($K_b = 0.3 \times 10^{-10}$) and *p*-chloro ($K_b = 1.5 \times 10^{-10}$) anilines are less basic. However, *p*-chloroaniline is significantly more basic of the two. Hence the exclusive formation of I (R = Cl) involving the more basic para amino group is understandable.

In contrast to chloroanilines, both *m*-toluidine ($K_b = 4.9 \times 10^{-10}$) and *p*-toluidine ($K_b = 12 \times 10^{-10}$) are more basic compared to aniline. Thus the formation of both I and II (R = CH₃) the former in larger proportion, from 4-methyl-*o*-phenylenediamine and acetylacetone can readily be understood.

Since both *m*-nitro ($K_b = 0.032 \times 10^{-10}$) and *p*-nitro ($K_b = 0.001 \times 10^{-10}$) anilines are far less basic than aniline, the inability of 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine to react with acetylacetone appears reasonable.

Experimental

1. *Condensation of 4-chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine with acetylacetone*: To a solution of 4-chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine (14.2 g, 100 m Mol) in acetic acid (100 ml) was added a similar solution of acetylacetone (12 g, 100 m Mol) at room temp. The mixture was stirred for 1 hr and diluted with cold water. The aqueous acid solution was made ammoniacal and extracted with chloroform. The dried chloroform extract after removal of the solvent was distilled under reduced pressure. *N*-(2-amino-4-chlorophenyl)-2,5-dimethyl pyrrole (11.2 g, 55%) b.p. 142°/2.5 mm. was obtained as a light brown solid which on passing through a column of alumina using petroleum ether as solvent yielded a colourless sample, m.p. 92°-3°. ν_{max} (3580 cm⁻¹, 3700 cm⁻¹ for -NH₂), NMR: δ 1.97 (6H, -CH₃); 3.42 (2H, -NH₂); 5.89 (2H, H in 2 and 3 of pyrrole) and 7.00 (3H, phenyl). Found: 12.92; C₁₂H₁₃ClN₂ requires N: 12.7%.

2. *Condensation of 4-methyl-*o*-phenylenediamine with acetylacetone*: 4-Methyl-*o*-phenylenediamine (12.2 g, 100 m Mol) was allowed to react with acetylacetone in the same way as above. The amino compound (13 g, 65%) was obtained on distillation at 122°-3°/1 mm. ν_{max} (3580 cm⁻¹ and 3720 cm⁻¹ for -NH₂), NMR: δ 1.92 (6H, -CH₃ in the pyrrole ring); 2.35 (3H, -CH₃ of the aromatic ring); 3.25 (2H, -NH₂), 5.77 (2H, H in 2 and 3 of pyrrole) and 6.66 (CH, phenyl ring). Found 13.92; C₁₃H₁₆N₂ requires N: 14.0%.

The compound was subjected to GLC (oven temp. 160°, main oven temp. 320° and injection temp. 310°) using apiezone column (30 m) when two peaks with retention times of 22.2 min. (60%) and 19.5 min. (40%) were observed. The former peak corresponded to I (R = CH₃).

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Kinetic Studies on the Coagulation Process of Ferric Arsenate Sol at Different Stages of Dialysis

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A NUMBER of papers¹⁻¹⁰ have appeared on the tyndallometric and extinction techniques that have been employed for following the coagulation process of a host of sols. The aforesaid techniques were used to investigate the process of coagulation of ferric arsenate sol by electrolyte amounts $\ll C_c$ (Coagulation Concentration) and far above this value at different stages of dialysis of the sol, and the record of Extinction-time curves is given in the present communication.

Experimental

Ferric arsenate sol was prepared and kept for dialysis in the same manner as described elsewhere¹¹. During the span of dialysis, three samples were withdrawn each representing a particular form of purity. The purity of the sol was assessed by viewing the reciprocal coagulation concentration of K₂SO₄ for each form of the sol (vide table 1) and the composition was determined in terms of Fe₂O₃, AsO₄³⁻, Cl- contents in gms/lit. The sols were coagulated with K₂SO₄ and the process of coagulation was studied by obtaining the plots of extinction (absorbance) *versus* time for different electrolyte concentrations lying in the vicinity of coagulation concentration and also in the range required for bringing about rapid coagulation. Use was made of Spekol Spectro-colorimeter set at 500 nm and the changes in extinction with the progress of time were recorded after mixing 10 ml of a particular electrolyte solution with 10 ml of the sol maintaining the same experimental conditions throughout the determination.

Discussion

Figs. 1 & 2 indicate that the sols show an auto-catalytic behaviour when coagulated with electrolyte concentrations $\ll C_c$. According to Verwey and Overbeek¹², who have developed the concept of de Boer¹³ and Hamaker¹⁴, the system behaves as a stable suspension in which the potential energy curves have a maxima \gg KT. Long range attraction is always a consequence of London-Vander Waals forces, but repulsion may originate in a variety of ways. For example, when the sols of not much purity